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**DETERMINATION OF VITAMINS IN MULTIVITAMIN COMPLEXES
USING HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY**

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Vitamins are biologically active compounds involved in important physiological processes in the body [1]. Preparations based on them are widely used in pharmacy. Determining the content of vitamins in various vitamin preparations such as vitamin-mineral complexes, as well as biologically active additives or food matrices is a necessary condition for monitoring the quality and safety of food products. In this regard, there is an urgent need to update the existing methodological base and increase its efficiency for the rapid, accurate, and reliable determination of vitamins in food products. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), as a universal and highly sensitive method of analysis, makes it possible to determine water- and fat-soluble vitamins in objects of complex natural origin, while being highly accurate and reproducible [2–4]. The HPLC method allows for separation with simultaneous quantitative determination of the content of vitamins when they are present together in food products. In Fig. Figure 1 shows an example of a chromatogram obtained using HPLC using ultraviolet detection (diode matrix), simultaneous quantitative determination of vitamins B1, B2, B6, PP in a multivitamin complex.

<Chromatogram>

mV

Fig. 1 Chromatogram of a multivitamin preparation. Vitamins - PP-4.485 min, B6-10.204 min, B2-12.441 min. B1- 13.836

The main advantages of the liquid chromatography method in relation to the analysis of vitamins are determined by its high accuracy and sensitivity, the ability to determine various forms of vitamins that are very similar in structure and properties; the ability to automate the process; wide range of concentrations of the determined compounds.

We studied 5 samples of multivitamin complexes using HPLC. The simultaneous determination of vitamins B1 (thiamine hydrochloride), B2 (riboflavin), PP (nicotinamide and nicotinic acid), B6 (pyridoxine) in multivitamin complexes obtained by us is presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Determination of vitamin content in samples

Analyzed objects	Vitamins			
	Thiamine	Riboflavin	Pyridoxine	Nicotinamide

	Passport		Found		Passport		Found	
	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab	mg/tab
Duovit	0,9-1,5	1,3±0,1	1,08-1,8	1,4±0,1	1,8-3	2,8±0,1	11,7-19,5	14,5±0,1
Komplivit	0,54-0,9	0	0,63-1,05	0,59±0,5	0,72-1,2	1,2±0,2	6,75-11,25	8,9±2
Vitarich	9-15	9,95±2	9-15	6,19±1	1,8-3	2,14±0,5	45-75	47,92±0,5
Supravit multiaktiv	2,7-4,5	3,82±0,5	1,8-3	0,14±0,5	4,5-7,5	5,42±0,5	18-30	20,67±2
Elevit	1,4-1,88	1,19±0,5	1,62-2.12	1,18±0,5	2,3-3,15	2,3±0,5	17,1-21,95	17,20±0,5

As can be seen from Table 1, the obtained results of duovite and elevit correspond to the passport data. Complivit does not contain vitamin B1; according to the passport data, the content of riboflavin (B2) in two samples of Vitarich and Supravit Multiactive was lower than the passport data.

The quantitative determination of vitamins B1, B2, B6 and PP in a mixture of vitamin-mineral complexes and biologically active additives from 5 samples was studied using the method of high-performance liquid chromatography. The results obtained were compared with regulatory documents and passport data. It was established that the Complivit samples did not contain vitamin B1; according to the passport data, the content of riboflavin (B2) in two samples Vitarich and Supravit Multi asset was lower than the passport data.

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